

AMRAAM BIT: OPERATIONAL BENEFITS AND PENALTIES

Andrew J. Burke, Jr., AFSC, Armament Division, Eglin AFB
Paul B. Guglielmoni, AFSC, Armament Division, Eglin AFB

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Abstract

The Advanced Medium Range Air-to-Air Missile (AMRAAM or AIM-120) currently in the Full-Scale Engineering Development Phase will replace the Sparrow as the beyond visual range armament for the Air Force's F-15 and F-16 and for the Navy's F-14 and F/A-18 fighter aircraft. Because it is a major Joint Service program with multinational implications, AMRAAM's reliability and maintainability requirements have received considerable attention. The program office has attempted to treat them rigorously so that meaningful readiness goals and thresholds can be articulated to DoD management at all levels of authority. To this end, a considerable number of analytical tasks have been performed on the affects of Built-in-Test on AMRAAM's operational performance over the defined life cycle of the missile. These analyses have led to the development of quantitative requirements for MTBFs, BIT effectiveness, and BIT false alarm rate which can be readily defended and which will be measured during all phases of the test program. The findings in some areas have been quite unexpected.

Introduction

The AMRAAM will be designed for: (1) ten years of dormant storage without preventative maintenance, (2) dormant captive carriage on all specified aircraft for at least fifty missions of two hours each, and (3) launch and free flight to the target. AMRAAM will be an All-Up-Round which implies limited maintenance of any kind in the field. This also intensifies the need for high reliability, both in storage and in flight, and for the effective utilization of BIT. The program office has modeled the mission profile to determine the affects of missile dormant and captive carry MTBF, BIT effectiveness, and BIT false alarm rate on the availability, operational reliability, and probability-of-kill of the missile. From a general viewpoint, BIT detects, diagnoses, and isolates faults in a system. On AMRAAM, BIT acts to remove from service some portion of the population of defective items which cannot perform their intended function. However, because BIT of all types exhibits the occasional tendency to falsely reject good systems, a proper balance of BIT effectiveness and BIT false alarm rate must be specified in order that availability is not unduly reduced. While there may be some tendency to overlook this simplistic outcome, it is critically important in achieving AMRAAM's readiness requirements. Bayes' equations, using AMRAAM specified diagnostic errors, have been used to understand and minimize the problem of an excessive number of fault-free missiles being returned to the depot, commonly called the RETOK (retest OK) or CND (cannot duplicate) problem. The analyses to date have resulted in the added use of a Missile BIT Tester at intermediate organizational maintenance level to simulate the proper aircraft-to-missile interface. This change to the concept is designed to detect falsely removed missiles and return them to operational usage before the unnecessary expenses of handling and transportation to a domestic depot.

AMRAAM Mission Profile

A simplified factory-to-target sequence for the AMRAAM missile was developed from the inputs of user organizations. The profile of Figure 1 is the anticipated sequence of events for the operational AMRAAM under an assumed wartime scenario. It consists of three principal parts: (1) dormant storage in a sealed container for as long as ten years without preventative maintenance, (2) operational use consisting of repetitive electronically dormant captive carriage on designated aircraft, and (3) launch and free flight to the target upon engaging the enemy. Built-in-Test (BIT) and Launch-to-Eject (LTE) are two automatic tests of AMRAAM conducted during captive carry and at trigger squeeze, respectively. Missile BIT Test (MBT) duplicates aircraft interface functions and is used after a missile fails BIT to preclude unnecessary return to a depot caused by aircraft system anomalies. Launch-to-Eject assures that certain safety criteria such as auto pilot functions are operational prior to missile release from the aircraft. It checks portions of the missile which cannot be analyzed by BIT due to restraints imposed by electrical power limitations and other design considerations.

Figure 1: AMRAAM Missile Profile

The factory-to-target sequence helps define two measures of merit of particular interest to AMRAAM: Mission Completion Success Probability and Operational Reliability.

Operational Reliability

Referring again to Figure 1, Mission Completion Success Probability is defined as the proportion of

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missiles which do not exit the mission profile at any point, i.e., the proportion of produced missiles which successfully arrives at a target without any repair action being required. Because Mission Completion Success Probability is unrealistically pessimistic in regard to maintenance actions normally caused by day-to-day operations, principally false alarms and other no-defect maintenance actions, the JSPO has concentrated on developing operational reliability as a principal measure of merit. Operational reliability for AMRAAM is defined as the probability of an effective missile (i.e., "good") after storage and a stipulated number of missions, given that the missile passed its first operational check on the aircraft using automated test equipment (BIT).

Figure 2 shows the probability-of-kill equation which has been developed from the mission profile.

RELIABILITY IMPACT ON P_k

$$P_k = \frac{\overbrace{P_a P_s^N (1-P_f)^{N+1}}^{\text{OPERATIONAL RELIABILITY RELATED}} \cdot \underbrace{P_g P_L P_h}_{\text{LETHALITY \& GUIDANCE}}}{[P_a (1-P_f) + (1-P_a) (1-P_b)] [P_s (1-P_f) + (1-P_s) (1-P_b)]^N}$$

- P_a = PROBABILITY THAT A MISSILE IS NONDEFECTIVE AFTER PRODUCTION, SHIPMENT, AND COMPLETION OF ONE YEAR IN READY STORAGE;
- P_b = PROBABILITY THAT BIT DETECTS A DEFECT;
- P_f = PROBABILITY THAT BIT REPORTS A NONEXISTENT DEFECT;
- P_s = PROBABILITY THAT COMPLETING 22-HOUR GROUND ENVIRONMENT (NONPOWERED), 2-HOUR CAPTIVE CARRY SORTIE, AND ARRESTED CARRIER LANDING WITHOUT ACQUIRING A NEW DEFECT;
- P_h = FREE FLIGHT RELIABILITY OF MISSILE
- N = NUMBER OF CAPTIVE CARRY SORTIES
- P_g = PROBABILITY THAT MISSILE SOFTWARE PROVIDES CORRECT GUIDANCE INFORMATION TO ARRIVE AT POINT WHERE WARHEAD DETONATION WOULD RESULT IN K-CLASS KILL
- P_L = PROBABILITY THAT WARHEAD INFLECTS SUFFICIENT DAMAGE ON TARGET TO SCORE K-CLASS KILL

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Figure 2: Operational Reliability's Influence on P_k

The equation consists of two factors: the first factor is the operational reliability of the AMRAAM system; the second factor contains terms relating to probability of good guidance, post launch reliability of hardware, and lethality.

The AMRAAM Joint Service Operational Requirements (JSOR) document is specific that a particular set of conditions will be used when reporting operational reliabilities. For AMRAAM, these conditions are that one year in ready storage (in a sealed container under exposed conditions) and the completion of fifty missions must be considered in the calculation of operational reliability. The JSOR further states that an operational reliability of at least .84 is the minimum acceptable for tactical use, and that .93 is, in fact, the desired level. The JSOR, and this discussion exclude from the definition of operational reliability the probability of a hardware failure during missile launch, and lethality (P_h and P_L respectively in the P_k equation). For this reason, all further discussion will be centered on operational reliability as the parameter of interest, not on P_k . The inclusion of the storage term P_a is of interest, because for BIT effectiveness less than 100%, undisclosable faults will accumulate in the missile population even during dormant storage, and will affect the number of missiles apparently good, but in fact, undisclosably bad at time of first BIT.

IMPACT OF BIT EFFECTIVENESS ON OPERATIONAL RELIABILITY

Figure 3: Influence of BIT Effectiveness on Operational Reliability

Figure 3 shows operational reliabilities plotted versus Mean Time Between Maintenance (MTBM) for Type I maintenance events for several levels of Built-In-Test (BIT) effectiveness. Shown are curves for 0% (no BIT), 60%, 70%, and 80%. For AMRAAM, effectiveness is considered to be that portion of the missile total failure rate, including that for irreversible functions and one-shot devices, which is disclosable by BIT. The JSOR imposes lower threshold and upper goal limits on BIT thoroughness which are 60% and 80%, respectively. Figure 4 indicates the current engineering estimate for AMRAAM BIT of approximately 71%.

MISSILE BIT THOROUGHNESS

ASSEMBLY	PERCENT OF FAILURE RATE (% λ_i)	ESTIMATED BIT EFFECTIVENESS (B_i)	BIT THOROUGHNESS (% λ_i) (B_i)
GUIDANCE SECTION			
RADOME SEEKER ASSY	15.6	.89	13.9
TRANSMITTER ASSY			
TRANSMITTER	7.9	.43	3.4
BATTERY (TX)	0.1	0	0
BATTERY (ECU)	0.2	0	0
BIT TRANSFORMER	0.1	1.00	0.1
ELECTRONICS UNIT	39.4	.87	34.2
ARMAMENT SECTION			
PROPULSION SECTION	1.6	0	0
CONTROL SECTION			
ACTUATOR SYSTEM			
ELECTROMECHANICAL	11.4	0	0
BATTERIES (4)	0.1	0	0
OTHER	23.4	.82	19.2
TOTALS	100.0	-	70.8

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Figure 4: Missile BIT Thoroughness

Figure 3 or the expanded view of the area of principal interest shown in Figure 5, indicates that without BIT an MTBM of approximately 575 is required

to meet the minimum JSOR threshold for operational reliability. The desired value of .93 can only be reached with an MTBM as high as approximately 1350 hours for AMRAAM without BIT. However, the use of BIT with an effectiveness of 60% to 80% based on the total failure rate can produce minimally acceptable operational reliabilities with MTBMs between 125 and 225 hours. The desired JSOR value of operational reliability of .93 can be achieved with MTBMs between about 225 hours and 475 hours, a significant reduction when compared to 1350 hours MTBM needed without BIT. Because relatively small changes in BIT effectiveness produce significant changes in operational reliability in the range of expected early missile MTBMs, an extensive practical evaluation of BIT effectiveness will be performed during approximately 25,000 total hours of AMRAAM combined environments test, analyze, and fix testing; operational captive carry reliability testing; and formal reliability testing.

Figure 5: Expanded MTBM Scale

If AMRAAM can be successfully developed to have an MTBM Type I of 1000 hours, which is the current contractual value, then BIT offers a six percentage point increase in operational reliability from .90 to .96 (see Figure 3). The impact of this increase in operational reliability can be better understood by reference to Figure 6.

AMRAAM LOADOUT	OPERATIONAL RELIABILITY			
	90 %		96 %	
	FAILURES	PROB	FAILURES	PROB
4 MISSILES	0	.6561	0	.850
	1	.2926	1	.141
	≥ 2	.0523	≥ 2	.009
6 MISSILES	0	.5315	0	.7828
	1	.3543	1	.1956
	≥ 2	.1142	≥ 2	.0215
8 MISSILES	0	.4315	0	.7214
	1	.3827	1	.2404
	≥ 2	.1868	≥ 2	.0381

PROBABILITY OF EXACT NUMBER OF DEFECTIVE MISSILES IN A GIVEN LOADOUT BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

Figure 6: Probability of Defective Missiles

The probabilities of having exactly zero, one, and two or more failed missiles in representative AMRAAM loads of 4, 6, and 8 missiles are presented for the two operational reliabilities of .90, and .96, respectively. The probability of carrying defective missiles on an aircraft is dramatically reduced through the use of BIT and its associated higher operational reliability. Again, these operational reliability numbers are calculated, conservatively, at the end of fifty missions in accordance with JSOR. Actual watime missions flown before missile launch will be considerably lower than fifty and, hence, the probability of carrying defective missiles will be lower than the probabilities shown in Figure 6.

False Alarm Rate

AMRAAM is being designed with a great preponderance of digital circuitry affording an opportunity for a more effective and reliable BIT scheme when compared to previous generation analog systems. However, no test system is perfect and allowances must be made for diagnostic errors caused principally by adverse tolerance build-ups, taken in combination with environmental extremes (although other causes may be prevalent as well). A good missile being called bad is called the false alarm rate. The AMRAAM System Specification has stipulated that the probability of a good missile being inadvertently (falsely) announced as being bad shall not exceed 2% for one BIT execution and shall not exceed 0.1% for two consecutive executions. The specification, therefore, recognizes some interdependence between BIT executions. Further, the system specification stipulates that BIT will be conducted once per mission, although from a practical standpoint, it will probably be used more often--perhaps as many as three times per mission.

Figure 7: Affect of False Alarm Rate on MCSP

Figure 7 indicates the impact on Mission Completion Success Probability of two different false alarm rates assuming one BIT execution per mission and a second BIT execution if a failed missile is indicated on the first execution. The curves are plotted for false alarm rates of 0.1% (the specified value) and for 1%, arbitrarily assumed to be ten times worse. The bottom two curves assume no Missile BIT Tester (MBT) at intermediate maintenance level and, hence, all missiles falsely removed from operations would have

to be returned to depot. The top two curves assume the use of a Missile BIT Test at intermediate level which duplicates aircraft-to-missile interface functions. With the MBT, missiles falsely removed during operations can be checked, essentially immediately, and returned to service without the expense and severe time penalty associated with return to depot.

False Return Rate

The False Return Rate is defined as the ratio of the number of missiles falsely determined to be bad and returned to the depot, to the total number of returns caused by true failures and false removals. This statistic is of interest to logisticians because every removal, whether caused by a "hard" failure or false alarm, requires the expenditure of maintenance manpower and associated resources. Returns to depot are extremely expensive.

Figure 8: Affect of False Alarm Rate on False Return Rate

False return rate is a function of false alarm rate, number missions flown, number of BIT executions, the ability to confirm failures, and other variables. Figure 8 indicates the false return rate for several false alarm rates. Other assumptions are listed on the Figure. One should exercise caution in attempting to perform any analysis based upon false return statistics because of the difficulties associated with definition of all the variables. Typical of this problem is the case where a confirmatory test set either has known design deficiencies, i.e., tolerance mismatches, or has not been maintained to the current software configuration of the operational equipment it is supposedly testing.

The composition of the population of fielded missiles can be determined using the classical statistical laws. Figure 9 shows the location of the missiles, i.e., on the aircraft, or in the repair pipeline and whether the missile is good or bad, as the number of missions is varied. Other assumptions are listed on the Figure. Several calculations of interest can readily be made from the information presented. For example, the operational reliability at 50 missions is calculated by taking the percent good on aircraft (78%), and dividing by the total number of missiles on aircraft (good plus bad, 78% + 5%) yielding approximately 94%. The percentage of

false removals in the return stream to the depot (no MBT is assumed) is approximately 24% (4%/17%) which as a crosscheck agrees with the .001 false alarm rate curve of Figure 8 at 50 missions.

False Removal Rate

Another statistic of interest, which will be considered later from a Bayesian viewpoint, is the instantaneous false removal rate. This ratio ignores the effects of failures caused by storage and considers only the "instantaneous" removals being caused by flight operations. From Figure 9, after the six percent of failures caused by storage is removed from consideration, the false removal rate at 50 missions is 4% false removals divided by the sum of false removals (4%) and bad in pipeline (true failures) caused by operations (6%). This value is approximately 40% estimated from the figure and will be shown later from a Bayesian calculation to be exactly 41.6%. This rate of false removals is clearly undesirable even if the falsely removed missiles are detected at the intermediate organizational level of repair. Further analysis will be shown indicating what alternatives may be available to alleviate this problem.

COMPOSITION OF FIELDIED MISSILES (WITHOUT MBT)

Figure 9: Composition of Fieldied Missiles

Bayesian Considerations

The issue of false removal rate is amenable to treatment through the use of Bayes' Theorem which is widely utilized as a basis for making statistical inferences. The theorem is presented here without derivation, but details are readily available in statistical texts. All test systems have some probability of calling a good system bad (a false, alarm) and a bad system good (a missed fault). Bayes formulas provided a means of converting a priori (before the fact) probabilities into a posteriori (after the fact) probabilities. This allows computation of the probability that a system has actually failed based on a test result. A more extensive treatment of this subject can be found in Reference 1. One form of Bayes Theorem is expressed by the equation:

$$P(A | B) = \frac{P(B | A) P(A)}{P(B | A) P(A) + P(B | \bar{A}) P(\bar{A})} \quad (1)$$

Where: A and B = arbitrary events

$P(A)$ and $P(B)$ = probabilities of events A and B

$P(A|B)$ = conditional probability of event A given that event B has occurred

$P(A,B)$ = joint probability of events A and B occurring together

$P(B) = P(B|A)P(A) + P(B|\bar{A})P(\bar{A})$ for the two alternative situation where A and \bar{A} are mutually exclusive events of which one necessarily occurs

For the specific AMRAAM case, the following definitions apply:

$R|F = B = .7$ The probability of a positive indication (a red light) given a fault exists

$G|F = 1-B = .3$ The probability of a negative indication (a green light) given a fault exists

$R|\bar{F} = L = .001$ The probability of a positive indication (a red light) given no fault exists

$G|\bar{F} = 1-L = .999$ The probability of a negative indication (a green light) given no fault exists

R = red light (positive)

G = green light (negative)

F = fault

\bar{F} = no fault

Also:

$1 - e^{-\frac{t}{MTBM}} = F = .002$ The probability of a missile failure in one two-hour mission with an MTBM of 1000 hours

$e^{-\frac{t}{MTBM}} = 1-F = .998$ The probability of no missile failure in one two-hour mission

These conditions are summarized in the following table:

True State	Probability of State	Prob of Green	Prob of Red
Fault	F	1 - B	B
No-Fault	1 - F	1 - L	L

Table 1

The possible diagnostic errors are: (1) a missed fault given by the probability 1-B; (2) a false alarm given by the probability L. By substituting into Bayes Formula (equation 1), the a posteriori probabilities for each possible case can

be calculated. These probabilities are listed in Table 2.

1	2	3	4
$P(F R)$	$P(\bar{F} R)$	$P(F G)$	$P(\bar{F} G)$
$\frac{FB}{FB + (1-F)L}$	$\frac{(1-F)(L)}{(1-F)(L) + FB}$	$\frac{F(1-B)}{F(1-B) + (1-F)(1-L)}$	$\frac{(1-F)(1-L)}{(1-F)(1-L) + F(1-B)}$
.5838	.4162	.0006	.9994

Table 2

Columns 1 and 2, which represent the cases where a red light has appeared (actually two consecutive lights as AMRAAM BIT is employed) show that 58% of these indications will be true positives (real faults) while 42% will be false positives (false alarms). This rate of false removals will not enthrall the logistics community. Alternatively, from column 4, pilots will be absolutely delighted because a green indication implies an extremely high probability that a missile has no test-detectable fault.

Prevalence of System Failure

The prevalence of failures in a system influences the number of false alarms (retest OKs) which are experienced. Malcolm, in Reference 1, dramatically illustrates this point. He concludes that "low prevalence of failures results in negative test results (green indications) being correct much more often than positive test results (red lights). This possibly explains a common phenomena that has been noted by maintenance personnel."

Figure 10: False Removal Rate Versus Prevalence of System Failure

Figure 10 indicates how the false positive rate (false removal rate) varies with prevalence of failure. This data is for AMRAAM specified values of missile MTBM, mission time, and false alarm rate. The currently estimated prevalence of AMRAAM failure per mission is .002 which yields a false removal rate of 41.6%. This result is for one BIT execution per two-hour mission. The false removal rate decreases dramatically as the prevalence of system failure is increased. The lower of the two curves indicates the reduction in false removal rate possible with a postulated order of magnitude reduction in false alarm rate. For AMRAAM's prevalence of failure of .002, only about 7% false removals would be experienced.

Figure 11 indicates the probability of no fault, given a green light indication, as a function of prevalence of system failure. For all reasonable AMRAAM levels of failure prevalence, the probability of no fault being present is extremely high and declines only slightly. The decline, in practical terms, has no significance to the pilot.

Figure 11: Probability of No Fault Versus Prevalence of System Failure

Implications of Low Prevalence of

Failure on AMRAAM

AMRAAM is expected to have a very low prevalence of failures by conventional military standards. Its MTBM for Type I maintenance actions is expected to be near 1000 hours for production versions of the missile. By comparison, many avionics black boxes have exhibited MTBMs in the range of 10-100 hours when tested under operational conditions. An increase in the frequency of BIT executions reduces the probability of equipment failure by reducing the time interval during which an actual failure can occur. The probability of experiencing a false alarm, however, is a function of the number of BIT executions and is independent of time. If AMRAAM were to experience three BIT executions per two-hour mission, the prevalence of failure would be reduced to approximately .00067 per BIT interval. Figure 10 indicates that not even an order of magnitude reduction in false alarm rate to 0.01% (1/10,000) would produce an acceptably low false removal rate for this very low prevalence of failure.

Conclusions

While AMRAAM BIT offers significant benefits in terms of increased operational reliability, the penalties associated with potentially excessive false removals must be a future consideration. For this reason, provisions have been made to evaluate AMRAAM's BIT performance throughout the development test program. In particular, BIT performance will be evaluated in development during approximately 17,000 hours of formal system level test, analyze, and fix testing; several thousand hours of operational captive carry testing; and as a condition of acceptance for each production lot of missiles. The discussion of technical alternatives which would alter specification requirements, for example, reducing the allowable false alarm rate, or logistics concept changes are beyond the scope of this discussion. Further studies will be conducted when test data becomes available.

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Biographies

Andrew J. Burke, Jr.
Air Force Systems Command/Armament Division
Deputy for Counterair
Eglin AFB, FL 32542

Mr Burke works for the Directorate of Technical Operations, Deputy for Counterair, as the Chief of the Product Assurance Division. He has responsibility for the R&M and quality assurance development activities for the Advanced Medium Range Air-to-Air Missile and other system elements. Mr Burke has a BChE from Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, and an MBA from the University of West Florida. He is ASQC Certified in Reliability and Quality Engineering with 17 years of Product Assurance experience in the acquisition of military equipment for the US Army and Air Force.

Paul B. Guglielmoni, Jr.
Air Force Systems Command/Armament Division
Deputy for Counterair
Eglin AFB, FL 32542

Mr Guglielmoni works for the Deputy for Counterair as lead reliability engineer on the Advanced Medium Range Air-to-Air Missile program. He is an American Society for Quality Control (ASQC) Certified Reliability Engineer with 10 years R&M experience in the acquisition of Air Force military equipment. Mr Guglielmoni has a BSAE from Florida Institute of Technology and an MS in Aeronautical Systems from the University of West Florida.